

UNDERSTANDING AND IMPLEMENTING PREMIS

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Abstract – This half day tutorial will provide participants with a short introduction to the PREMIS Data Dictionary as well as to basic methods of implementations. The goal is for attendees to have a basic understanding of what PREMIS is, how digital preservation metadata can be used in processes and how the data dictionary can be implemented in workflows and systems.

Submission Type: Tutorial.

Keywords: metadata, strategy, training, preservation metadata

Conference Topics: Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

While this tutorial has been given before at different instances of iPRES, the PREMIS standard continuously evolves, and this evolution and growth is respectively reflected in the tutorial. New examples and experiences feed into the tutorial to be given at iPRES 2025. Furthermore, the PREMIS tutorial has not been given often in Australia/Oceania/Asia, and we propose to give a 3 hours tutorial (or 90 min. at least) This will enable better audience engagement and maximize learning and take-away during exercises that will be incorporated throughout the agenda.

The PREMIS Data Dictionary is a description of structured metadata for preservation. This metadata captures information that plays a vital role in enabling the effective management, discovery, and re-usability of digital information. Preservation metadata provides provenance information, documents preservation activity, identifies technical features, and aids in verifying the authenticity of digital objects. PREMIS is a core set of metadata

elements (called “semantic units”) which is very beneficial to use in all preservation repositories regardless of the type of materials archived, the type of institution, and the preservation strategies employed.

The PREMIS Data Dictionary was originally developed by the Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies (PREMIS) Working Group in 2005 and revised in 2008 and 2015. It is maintained by the PREMIS Editorial Committee and the PREMIS Maintenance Activity is managed by the Library of Congress [1].

We have seen a constant call for PREMIS to undertake tutorials, such as this, as more and more organizations come to grips with digital preservation.

The tutorial aims at developing and spreading awareness and knowledge about metadata to support the long-term preservation of digital objects.

II. FORM OF THE TUTORIAL

We prefer an on-the-premise tutorial, since the interaction with the audience can provide a much better result. However, although it is recommended to avoid a hybrid tutorial, we will gladly present it as such if needed. It will be with focus on the participants in the room, but where a video transmission can allow virtual participants to follow the tutorial and ask questions e.g. in a google doc document or via a chat. We encourage collaborative note taking by the participants, which is a task easily shared by on-site as well as virtual participants.

III. SUMMARY OF THE TUTORIAL

This tutorial provides in its first part an introduction to PREMIS and its data model and an examination of the semantic units in the Data Dictionary organized by the entities in the PREMIS data model, objects, events, agents and rights.

The second part of the tutorial presents how the preservation community can use PREMIS metadata support tools for the implementation of software, repository systems and data management practices.

The third part of the tutorial presents high level examples and case studies of PREMIS implementation, using PREMIS in XML and PREMIS in RDF, in relation to the PREMIS Ontology.

Throughout the tutorial we will include examples of implementation experiences which are built upon through the institutional experiences of the tutors.

The tutorial includes exercises. These will be run and discussed during the tutorial session. However, questions asked regarding the data model and basic PREMIS functionality will be prioritised. If high audience interaction throughout the main part of the tutorial leaves no room for exercises to be run during the allocated time slot, only a brief introduction to the exercises is given and they will be given as take-home exercises. In either scenario, answers to the exercises are included in the materials.

IV. CONTENT OUTLINE

The draft outline for the tutorial is outlined below.

- 1) Introduction to PREMIS
 - Background (brief history and rationale of PREMIS)
 - Benefits of implementing PREMIS
- 2) PREMIS in detail
 - Outline of main Entities in the Data Model with Examples and Exercises
- 3) Implementation
 - PREMIS with other standards, e.g. METS
 - Case studies
 - Support and the PREMIS community
 - Conformance
- 4) Next Steps
 - Round table discussion for institutional plans
- 5) Wrap up

Time for questions and comments is planned between the different sections of the outline.

V. CONCLUSION

Participants will after the tutorial understand:

- 1) What PREMIS is and why it exists;
- 2) The benefits of implementing PREMIS;
- 3) The nature of the existing PREMIS community;
- 4) The critical role PREMIS plays in the digital preservation community.

In addition, participants will get insight into:

- 1) How PREMIS may be used in conjunction with other metadata standards;
- 2) How different organizations implement PREMIS within their own repositories;
- 3) How PREMIS, deals with Semantic Web Technology

REFERENCES

- [1] PREMIS website. Accessed 2025. Located at <http://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/index.html>. archived in web archived: archive.org, archive time: 2025-02-13T02:03:44 UTC.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Karin Bredenberg is a Metadata Strategist at the municipality organization Sydarkivera. She currently serves as the chair of PREMIS EC, co-chair of TS EAS, chair of the DILCIS Board as well as a member of the METS Board.

Eld Zierau has been a member of the PREMIS Editorial Committee, since 2013. She is a Senior Researcher in digital preservation at the Royal Danish Library, and she has worked with digital preservation since 2007.

Micky Lindlar joined the PREMIS Editorial Committee in 2019. At TIB Micky leads the Digital Preservation Team, responsibilities of that role include the oversight of a digital preservation system which is used for TIB's own holdings as well as for a Digital-Preservation- as-a-Service solution.

